

Yangsheng Daoism from Laozi to Ge Hong

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Early Daoist studies has two main schools of thought: associated with Chinese scholarship, the first holds that Laozi 老子 was born circa 571 BC and that he composed the Daodejing 道德經; associated with Western scholarship, the second holds that Laozi never lived and that the Daodejing was anonymously compiled from existing sources around 250 BC. Because views that argue for the existence of Laozi and his “authorship” of the Daodejing are relatively scarce in Western studies, this entry supports the former views, namely by maintaining Laozi’s historical existence and his central involvement with the earliest circulations of the Daodejing, but it also departs from them in some significant ways. Developing these views opens new ways to understand early Daoist groups and their commitment to the teachings of the Daodejing. By the beginning of the Warring States, the Daodejing was already circulating in certain Daoist interpretive communities. Given that their understandings of the text’s philosophy of the Dao were not identical, their commitment to it nevertheless united them in ways that justify the application of the Daoist label to them. These groups included Yangsheng Daoists 養生道, who prioritized the practice of the Daodejing’s teachings of bodily cultivation called yangsheng 養生 (nourishing life); Fangxian Daoists 方仙道, who modified yangsheng from a self-directed cultivation to an other-directed therapeutic or medical tradition; Zuowang Daoists 坐忘道, who supported the Daodejing’s philosophy of the Dao but who distanced themselves from yangsheng bodily cultivation in favor of the zuowang 坐忘 spiritual cultivation that was endorsed by the Xinshu 心術 texts from the Guanzi 管子 as well as the Zhuangzi 莊子; and Huang-Lao Daoists 黃老道, who absorbed zuowang spiritual cultivation even as they transformed the Daodejing’s original phenomenology of the Dao into a metaphysics. Of these four titles, only Fangxian Daoism and Huang-Lao Daoism are directly recognized in the contemporary historical sources, while Yangsheng Daoism and Zuowang Daoism are not, in part due to the relative absence of elitist writers who would recognized their existence, although later writers would collectively refer to these groups as Lao-Zhuang 老莊; this is an important factor in the Western habit to deny their existence. This entry focuses on Yangsheng Daoism as the original group that demonstrates a commitment to Laozi’s teachings on yangsheng as a self-directed bodily cultivation. As it is portrayed in several sections of the Zhuangzi and the Liexian zhuan 列仙傳, whose composition is traditionally attributed to Liu Xiang 劉向 (77-8 BCE), as well as throughout the two works of Ge Hong 葛洪 (283-343), the Baopuzi 抱朴子 and the Shenxian zhuan 神仙傳, the unique nexus of Yangsheng Daoism is its three-part structure: entering the mountains, becoming disciple to a Daoist master, and committing to the techniques of yangsheng to acquire long life. As a general term, yangsheng is synonymous with xingqi 行氣 (“qi circulation”), qigong 氣功 (“qi cultivation”), and tuna 吐納 or, more precisely, tugu naxin 吐古納新 (“to spit out the old and take in the new [qi]”), practices that are often set next to the postures and movements of daoyin 導引 (to push and pull), a kind of calisthenics often performed in imitation of animal behaviors, that intend to “push” the new qi throughout the body. Ge Hong, who repeatedly self-identified with this tradition of Laozi’s Daoism, presented its first systematic exposition. According to him, yangsheng as a category marker consists of four relatively autonomous practices of bodily cultivation: xingqi; daoyin; sexual arts (房中之術 fangzhong zhi shu); and 服飯 fushi (dietetics) centered on 辟谷 bigu (grain avoidance). Although Yangsheng Daoist writings represent yangsheng as having an ancient pedigree, its original textual demonstrations are found throughout the verses of the Daodejing without directly naming it. It is a term that many other Warring States texts variously used sometimes with meanings different from Laozi in contexts other than bodily cultivation, including the Guoyu 國語, Zhuangzi, Mengzi 孟子, Xunzi 荀子, Guanzi, Sunzi Bingfa 孫子兵法, and Lüshi Chunqiu 呂氏春秋. The term yangsheng gave rise to a collection of cognate terms, all which center on long life, including 養壽 yang shou, 養長 yang chang, and 養老 yang lao (nourishing

long life), 養形 yang xing (nourishing the form), 養身 yang shen (nourishing the torso), 養氣 yang qi (nourishing breath), 養己 yang ji (nourishing self), 養神 yang shen (nourishing spirit), 養德 yang de (nourishing circulation or nourishing virtue), 養性 yang xing (nourishing nature), 養心 yang xin (nourishing heart-mind), and 養耳目 yang ermu (nourishing ears and eyes). Yangsheng and related terms are found with more prevalence in the Han, and then became a staple term in a wide array of Chinese philosophical and medical writings thereafter. The writings of Yangsheng Daoism are noteworthy for their consistent application of yangsheng to techniques of bodily cultivation. In the Daodejing, Laozi concentrates on xingqi and daoyin but, at least on the surface, he has less to say about fangzhong zhi shu and bigu. The text presents the theoretical underpinnings of yangsheng by way of its phenomenology of the Dao; it states, for example, that “the Great Dao pervades everything, it goes round and round” (34). It also states, “Looked at but not seen, it is invisible; listened to but not heard, it is inaudible; reached for but not felt, it is intangible” (14). An important element of this phenomenology is the notion of qi, understandable as the breath of the Dao that serves as the very stuff of all life: being formless, it is the air that nourishes all beings; taking form, it is that which congeals to manifest the substantiality of all things and beings. The expansive (陽 yang) and contractive (陰 yin) movements of qi function together in systems of circulation that are applicable in many areas and are everywhere apparent: in atmospheric phenomena visible in the sky and the change of the seasons, in oceanic tides, in the veins of rocks and leaves and, in the context of yangsheng bodily cultivation, in the body’s numerous systems of circulation. Because human beings are an organic part of the world, our lives, together with all other living beings, are defined by qi; mirroring Laozi’s philosophy of the Dao, Zhuangzi Chapter 22 writes that “the accumulation of qi is life; its dispersal is death.” Yangsheng consists of the techniques that allow a person to prolong his or her life by expelling debilitating, exhausted qi from the body and replenishing it with vital, pristine qi. Xingqi is the fundamental method for this, especially when one absorbs air in its purest form as found on mountains; daoyin serves to circulate it throughout the body; fangzhong zhi shu lets people exchange and rebalance their qi either by taking yin and giving yang or taking yang and giving yin; and bigu concerns the foods and drinks that further empower or debilitate the body. Referring to these practices, Daodejing Chapter 22 states that “bending leads to intactness; twisting leads to straightness; depletion leads to renewal; reduction leads to increase.” Chapter 45 also states, “Great filling seems to be incomplete, yet its usefulness is never exhausted. Great straightening seems to be bent... Activity overcomes cold, tranquility overcomes heat, and calmness and tranquility regulate the world.” Among various theories about the ancient origins of yangsheng, some point to an hunter-gather realization of the benefits of deep breathing to enhance physical strength and endurance, which is related to xingqi, while others emphasize the imitation of animal behaviors, thus raising shamanism as ancient precursor to yangsheng, especially in the context of Zhuangzi 15’s description of yangsheng masters who practice “bear-hangings and bird-stretches” and the Daoyintu’s 導引圖 visual representations of multiple other animal-based daoyin movements. The Daoist understanding of its origins is somewhat more complex since it sees yangsheng woven into the very fabric of existence. The Liexian zhuan, for example, recognizes a certain Rong Chengzi 容成子, already alive at the dawn of human existence, as the pioneering human who first discovered and understood it, but he did not invent it. He initially mastered fangzhong zhi shu, identified with the Mysterious Female (玄牝 xuanpin) and the Spirit of the Valley (穀神 gushen), which, towards the end of his long life, he personally taught to Laozi who himself directly named them in Daodejing Chapter 6. Ge Hong, writing about “the many hermits who honor the techniques of Laozi,” also does not recognize Laozi as the inventor of yangsheng but rather sees him as its greatest teacher who also composed the Daodejing. Further, because “the moisture of Laozi’s vast spring that has long flowed forth is abundant, abundant,” he further writes that Laozi was “established by Heaven and Earth as the teacher for ten thousand generations.” From its earliest circulations, the Daodejing served as the orientational text for the Yangsheng Daoist nexus of entering the mountains, becoming disciple to a hermit master, and committing to yangsheng and the pursuit of longevity. Even if the earliest Daoist communities did not systematically fulfill this nexus in every way, considering it allows us to reconstruct the ways in which writings from Laozi to Ge Hong understood it. Accordingly, members of these mountainous communities shared a common goal in their pursuit of longevity by means of yangsheng, which they learned from yangsheng masters that the Daodejing refers to as sages (聖人 shengren). But because the term was also central to other political writings of the time whose circulations were far more widespread, in which sages systematically referred to

rulers at the head of enlightened government, by the time of the Zhuangzi, Daoist writings began to embrace xian 仙 as a distinguished term for those who had achieved long life. It became a staple term in the Daoist lexicon of the Liexian zhuan, the Baopuzi, and the Shenxian zhuan, where it also absorbed the additional meaning of immortals for some of the xian. In addition to their mountainous communities committed to yangsheng, Yangsheng Daoists were also the original framers, editors, and interpreters of the teachings of the Daodejing, which in their earliest version likely took the form of oral teachings transmitted from masters to their disciples. During the early Warring States, some adherents successfully modified yangsheng from a self-directed bodily cultivation to an other-centered medical therapy, which they then exported to a wealthy clientele in society. As represented in texts such as the Shiji 史記, these medical professionals were called fangji 方技, and they belonged to a tradition called Fangxian Daoism whose practice, according to David Schaberg, combined yangsheng therapies with recitations of the Daodejing. These developments provide the deeper historical contexts for understanding Fangxian Daoism's later and more sophisticated writings as seen, for example, in two of their texts unearthed from Zhangjiashan dated to 186 BCE, the Maishu 脈書 and Yinshu 引書), as well as the six unearthed from Mawangdui dated to 168 BCE, including the Daoyintu, Yangsheng fang 養生方, Shiwen 十問, and He Yinyang 和陰陽, which Donald Harper has studied in great depth. This exposure of the Daodejing to elite members of society, albeit in originally medical contexts, drew the attention of learned philosophers as well as leading politicians, and it brought the text's philosophy of the Dao to new levels of widespread familiarity. The first group that formed from this is called Huang-Lao Daoism, a separate tradition that formed around the middle of the Warring States. They distanced yangsheng teachings from the text's philosophy of the Dao, and they went on to transform this philosophy from a phenomenology to a powerful metaphysics with starkly political overtones that was directed to the enlightened ruler. Their Dao was no longer at home in the world, but rather represented a transcendental entity that the ruler could mystically access; having done so, he was then empowered to translate the Dao's eternal principles, including ziran 自然 and wuwei 無為, into his utopian Daoist government. Although historical records that would shed light on the continuation of the mountainous tradition of Yangsheng Daoism throughout the course of the Han are relatively scarce, the Liexian zhuan, standing as the first known collection of xian biographies, fills in this void. Consisting of some 72 xian biographies, only a handful are focused on Yangsheng Daoists, while the majority consist of fables and legends of those who acquired long life by means other than yangsheng; for example, one biography tells of a commoner who encountered a dragon with a toothache, and after extracting the tooth, the dragon gifted the person with long life. The historical record concerning Yangsheng Daoism remains mostly quiet until Ge Hong's Shenxian zhuan and Baopuzi. The former represents the second collection of xian biographies, around 80 depending on the edition, a handful of which are revised versions of biographies also found in the Liexian zhuan. The much larger number of its biographies concentrate on Yangsheng Daoists, many of which come with an innovative twist. Ge Hong presents the xian in two broad categories, namely dixian 地仙 and tianxian 天仙, with one subcategory identified with each. Virtually all these xian meet the criteria of the yangsheng nexus by entering the mountains where they find a teacher, either human or divine, under whom they master yangsheng and acquire long life. However, the dixian remain on the earth where they continue to reside in the mountains, except for the subcategory of householder xian who divide their time between their household and the mountains; this is exemplified in the biography of Peng Zu 彭祖. The tianxian, on the other hand, first master yangsheng and acquire long life before they graduate to the complex operations of alchemy and, after producing and ingesting a divine elixir, they acquire immortality and ascend directly into the heavens, where they are to positions in the celestial bureaucracy. The subcategory of tianxian is called shijie 屍解, referring to those xian who, after ingesting the elixir, ascend to the heavens "by way of release from the corpse." Although yangsheng was given the highest priority in Ge Hong's writings, they profoundly influenced later traditions of Daoist religion that prioritized alchemy, especially neidan 內丹 (inner alchemy) that was less concerned with laboratory operations than with a spiritualized form of transformation, but they did not meet the yangsheng nexus criteria; instead, their nexus was grounded in formal ordination into a specific order and was centered in temples and included large doses of devotional practices. Nonetheless, Yangsheng Daoism continued unabated, as even Michel Strickmann recognizes for the period of medieval China, although its adherents did not bequeath many records of their tradition or their mountainous lives. More recently, there have been

a few modern studies of this tradition that do not specifically recognize it as Yangsheng Daoism as such, including Bill Porter's *Road to Heaven: Encounters with Chinese Hermits*, which is a record of his encounters with Daoist mountain hermits. Another valuable contemporary contribution that, however, focuses on Daoist monastic communities residing on mountains is *Dream Trippers: Global Daoism and the Predicament of Modern Spirituality* by David Palmer and Elijah Siegler, but it also has valuable things to say about the Daoist mountainous hermit tradition.

Date Range: 571 BCE - 343 CE

Region: China proper

Region tags: Asia, East Asia, China

The heartland of China excluding ethnic borderlands such as Mongolia, Tibet, and Xinjiang

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Michael, Thomas. 2022. *Philosophical Enactment and Bodily Cultivation: In the Matrix of the Daodejing*. London: Bloomsbury.
- Source 2: Michael, Thomas. 2015. *In the Shadows of the Dao: Laozi, the Sage, and the Daodejing*. Albany: State University of New York Press.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Yangsheng_\(Daoism\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Yangsheng_(Daoism))
- Source 1 URL: [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Yangsheng_\(Daoism\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Yangsheng_(Daoism))
- Source 1 Description: Wikipedia entry on yangsheng
- Source 2 URL: [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Xian_\(Taoism\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Xian_(Taoism))
- Source 2 Description: Wikipedia entry on xian

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://ctext.org/dao-de-jing>
- Source 1 Description: 道德經
- Source 2 URL: <https://ctext.org/lie-xian-zhuan>
- Source 2 Description: 列仙傳
- Source 3 URL: <https://ctext.org/shen-xian-zhuan>
- Source 3 Description: 神仙傳

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– No

Notes: As one tradition of Daoism next to others (Fangxian Daoism, Huang-Lao Daoism, and later, Tianshi Daoism), Yangsheng Daoism was the earliest from which the later traditions emerged and developed, particularly in their commitment to the founding text of Daoism, the Daodejing. Nevertheless, being a tradition of mountainous hermits, Yangsheng Daoism had little contact with them. In the post-Han period, Ge Hong represents Yangsheng Daoists as having a limited contact with the common people, especially in the context of providing health services from time to time.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: Yangsheng Daoism was structured on master-disciple relations that were freely chosen by both parties, and this is often represented as taking place in the mountains.

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– No

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: The Yangsheng Daoist masters are never represented as having any kind of outreach, however, they are sometimes represented as temporarily sojourning in villages and helping the locals with medical issues where they make themselves available to prospective disciples.

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: This changes with the tianxian (heavenly xian) as represented in the Shenxian zhuan, where they are represented as actively seeking wealthy and powerful sponsors who will support their alchemical operations.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Being a tradition of mountain hermits, they are impossible to number.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Being a tradition of mountain hermits, they are impossible to number.

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: The Daodejing is the foundational text of virtually all forms of Daoism, however, Yangsheng Daoism did not treat it as a sacred or revealed scripture; it was the record of the teachings of Laozi that was considered worthy of exceptional esteem.

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

Notes: The Daodejing was originally an oral text and represented the main content of the verbal transmissions from master to disciples, together with the transmissions of yangsheng techniques, which were taught by hands-on methods. The Shenxian zhuan and Baopuzi mention a few writings that discussed specific techniques of yangsheng practice, but their precise techniques could not be specifically recorded in ways that a person could master by themselves without direct supervision.

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– No

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Inspired by high god:

– No

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– Yes

Notes: The teachings of the Daodejing, together with the composition of the text itself, are systematically attributed to Laozi. Although Laozi's biography in the Shenxian zhuan presents the legend that Laozi composed the Daodejing for the border guard, Yin Xi, when he was said to leave China, this seems to be a capitulation to mainstream Han Dynasty views, since other discussions of Laozi within the Yangsheng Daoist context, including sections of the Zhuangzi as well as the Shenxian zhuan and the Baopuzi, present him as a mountain hermit (who may or may not have held an official position in the Zhou bureaucracy earlier in his life), where the Daodejing formed as the body of his oral teachings. Looked at in this way, the name "Laozi" may simply stand for "the Old Masters" as a collective term for the earliest yangsheng masters, whose teachings were gathered into the (originally oral) text that came to be called the Daodejing.

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– Yes

Notes: There are multiple versions of the Daodejing belonging to the different traditions of Daoism that are seen in specific editions appropriate to each version. Because there are no complete editions the Yangsheng version (the excavated Guodian editions are the closest we have, but they represent only a portion of the complete text, as we have come to know it), we have no way to know its degree of oral fluidity and to what degree any given master would have altered it in recitation and transmission, but this would have entailed only a limited measure of alterability that would not have changed the total body of its teachings.

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions:

– No

Notes: No other external institutions outside of Yangsheng Daoism would have affected the Yangsheng interpretations of the text.

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by officially sanctioned figures:

– Yes

Notes: Those who originally produced the teachings of the text (Laozi as a single person or Laozi as a corporate entity) had the original authority to interpret the teachings. Because of the later Yangsheng structure of master-disciple transmissions, transmitting masters had the sole authority to interpret them to their immediate disciples.

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: Those persons trained in transmitting the teachings of the Daodejing were the disciples who would then become masters.

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– No

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: Mountainous regions were the primary environment for the practice of yangsheng, due to their relative quiet coupled with the purity of the mountain air, the most important component of yangsheng.

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Notes: Pilgrimages to sacred sites are not recorded in the writings, however, potential students entered the mountains in search of masters who they may or may not have known by reputation before meeting them.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– No

Notes: Yangsheng Daoism is founded on the non-separability of body and spirit, but more than this, it is founded on the view that sees the living human person made up of three primary components: jing that refers to the blood and other fleshly elements of the body; qi that refers to the breath but which, in its hardened form, forms the skelton; and shen that refers to the spirit. Their separation defines death, while life is defined by their being held together. Yangsheng consists of the techniques that allow the adept to keep them together in vitality, which is the single method for acquiring long life.

Belief in afterlife:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Field doesn't know

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– Field doesn't know

Are formal burials present:

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– No

Notes: The Liexian zhuan and the Shenxian zhuan present some xian who are divine and who reside in xian-lands that are mostly inaccessible to normal human beings, but it is not always clear if they began their lives as humans or were spiritual beings from their beginning. Many of the xian are represented as having abilities that border on the supernatural, first of all in their long lives, but also in their near-miraculous abilities to heal people sometimes even after they were pronounced dead. In the writings of Ge Hong, there is a highly sophisticated understanding of supernatural beings, the high gods of the Dao as well as a developed spiritual bureaucracy, but that was in many ways separate from the classical Yangsheng Daoist views, even as those classical views continued to inform his writings on the dixian.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– No

Notes: Although the supernatural beings, when present, do not mete out punishment, the xian are sometimes recorded as denying access to the teachings of those who are deemed unworthy of them, and this judgment is not based in morality as much as it based on the purity or lack thereof of their physical bodies.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Notes: Again, the highest reward, whether from a yangsheng master or from a divine xian, are the bestowal of yangsheng teachings that can lead the practitioner to the acquisition of long life.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– No

Notes: There are little if any moral virtues prescribed by Yangsheng Daoism, however, there are strict physical virtues required for acceptance by a yangsheng master; a clear example is found in the Shenxian zhuan's biography of Liu Gen. When he encountered a divine xian in the mountains, he was told, " You must have the bones of a xian, which is why you are able to see me. But at present your marrow is not full, your blood is not warm, your breath is weak, your brain is soft, your sinews are slack, and your flesh is damp... If you desire to acquire long life, you must first cure your illness."

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: In fact, one fundamental practice of yangsheng is fangzhong zhi shu, "the bedroom arts," which are sexual techniques for the exchange of yin and yang between sexual partners.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males):

– No

↳ Monogamy (females):

– No

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: For males and females, sexual activity is to be performed within a yangsheng context and not motivated by lust, passion, or the desire for offspring.

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Notes: For males and females, sexual activity is to be performed within a yangsheng context and not motivated by lust, passion, or the desire for offspring.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Notes: Bigu or the avoidance of grains requires a drastic reduction of food intake, and many xian are described as going for extended periods without eating food, but this is very different from deliberate fasting.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Notes: Bigu recommends certain foods to ingest, primary of which are the natural growths of herbs and roots found on the mountains, but there is little mention of any food taboos as such.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: The religious group is organized by way of master-disciple lineages.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– No

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: Adherents appear to mainly subsist on the natural roots, plants, and other products found on mountains that they gather for themselves.

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Gathering

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Bibliography

General References

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